

When AI Cites Unverified Data to Estimate AI Trustworthiness: A Real-Time Observation of Information Laundering via Media Distribution Chains

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Abstract

This report documents a real-time observation conducted on June 23, 2026. Beginning with an experiment to test whether Copilot recognized EuSpRIG as an academic organization, the author traced a chain of events in which an AI system cited unverified survey data to estimate the proportion of users who accept AI outputs uncritically. The survey data originated from a corporate press release distributed via PRTIMES and subsequently republished by multiple Japanese news outlets without verification. The core finding is a self-referential paradox: data measuring AI trustworthiness was itself accepted without verification by the AI systems and media outlets distributing it.

1. Initial Observation

On June 23, 2026, the author used Microsoft Copilot to test whether EuSpRIG (European Spreadsheet Risks Interest Group) would be recognized as an academic organization. EuSpRIG was not returned in results for "world's leading Excel expert organizations." When queried directly, Copilot described EuSpRIG as an informal hobbyist group. The author corrected this mischaracterization and noted that individuals without domain knowledge would have no means to identify this as an error.

2. The Question of Believability

Following the correction, the author asked Copilot to estimate what proportion of users would accept such misinformation without verification. Copilot answered: 8%.

3. Source Identification

The author identified the source of the 8% figure as a press release published by ADTANK Co., Ltd. (Tokyo) via PRTIMES on June 2, 2026. The release reported results of what it described as a large-scale survey (approximately 20,000 responses) on consumer trust in AI-generated answers.

4. Methodology Examination

Examination of the survey methodology revealed the following:

- Survey method: YouTube Community Poll
- The YouTube channel used was not identified in the release
- No independently verifiable channel associated with ADTANK was found
- Sample composition: unknown, as YouTube Community Polls reach only existing channel subscribers
- Survey instrument: a single self-report question asking respondents how much they trust AI search results
- No third-party verification or academic review

The 8% figure represented respondents selecting “I trust it completely and use it as-is.” The remaining 67% selected “I mostly trust it but verify myself” — a response category that the release aggregated with the 8% to claim “75% trust AI answers.”

5. Distribution Chain

The press release was republished on the same day by the following outlets:

- Tokyo Shimbun (clearly labeled as PRTIMES content)
- Asahi Shimbun (source attribution not immediately visible)
- Impress Watch

Google search results confirmed simultaneous visibility of all four sources (ADTANK, Asahi, Tokyo Shimbun, Impress) for the query “ADTANK 2万人 AIリテラシー 新聞” as of June 23, 2026. These search results are archived as supporting material.

6. Structural Observation

The press release included a description of ADTANK's commercial service "PR x AIO Consult," which explicitly lists "Research PR (survey releases)" as a method for creating content that AI systems will learn from and cite. The survey release used to generate the 8% figure is itself an example of this service category.

This creates a self-contained structure:

1. A commercial service sells the creation of survey releases designed to be cited by AI
2. The company demonstrates this service by publishing a survey release
3. The release is distributed via PRTIMES and republished by news outlets
4. AI systems learn from these outlets and cite the figure
5. The citation validates the commercial service

7. The Self-Referential Paradox

The data used by Copilot to estimate the proportion of users who accept AI outputs uncritically was itself accepted without verification by:

- The news outlets that republished it
- The AI system that cited it

The survey's central claim — that only 8% of users accept AI answers uncritically — was distributed and cited in a manner consistent with uncritical acceptance.

Supporting Materials

All source documents are archived with this record:

- Original article webpage.pdf
- PR TIMES article webpage.pdf
- Tokyo Shimbun article webpage.pdf
- Asahi Shimbun article webpage.pdf
- IMPRESS article webpage.pdf
- Google search results.png
- Copilot Interaction 1.pdf
- Copilot Interaction 2.pdf